

Review Article

Why nanoelectrochemistry is necessary in battery research?

Edgar Ventosa^{1,2}**Abstract**

The active materials constitute the heart of any battery so that unambiguous determination of their intrinsic properties is of essential importance to achieve progress in battery research. A variety of in situ techniques with high lateral resolution has been developed or adapted for battery research. Surprisingly, nanoelectrochemistry is not attracting sufficient attention from the battery community despite the existing examples of relevant in situ and highly resolved spatiotemporal information. Herein, the important role of nanoelectrochemistry in battery research is highlighted to help encourage its use in this field. In the first part, two examples in which the use of nanoelectrochemistry is a must are provided, that is, determination of intrinsic kinetics of active materials and understanding of relationships between particle structure and electrochemical activity. In the second part, pros and cons of three mature nanoelectrochemistry techniques in battery research, that is, particle-on-a-stick measurements, nanoimpact measurements, and scanning electrochemical probe microscopy, are discussed providing representative examples.

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Introduction

Batteries have revolutionized our society, enabling commercial success of various smart devices used in day-

to-day life, for example, portable electronics (mobile phones, tablets, and so on). More importantly, batteries are also the power sources of choice for the emerging electrified transport model as well as the energy storage technologies necessary for relying on renewable energy sources, for example, wind and solar radiation. Consequently, interest in developing new battery chemistries and improving existing battery technologies has gained much attention in recent years. Although the basic composition of a battery can be simply summarized into three elements, that is, positive electrode, electrolyte solution, and negative electrode, it is not a simple electrochemical device at all. Many electrochemical processes occur simultaneously, which hinder unambiguous investigation of the separate reactions and components. Aware of it, the battery research community has devoted much effort in developing and adapting advanced characterization techniques, which help putting together all pieces of the scientific puzzle. Without proper understanding of the individual elements of the complex system, progress in battery research at the cell level cannot be achieved. In general, efforts have been focused on the development of two groups of techniques. (1) *In situ* and *operando* techniques are of vital importance because information is obtained under relevant conditions (as close as possible to operating conditions) [1–3]. (2) Spatially resolved techniques allow the study of a group of individuals instead of evaluating the average response of thousands [4–6]. The battery research community has shown high interest in several advanced techniques, for example, in situ transmission electron microscopy as illustrated by the large number of citations attracted by pioneering works [7–9]. Surprisingly, efforts in nanoelectrochemistry and microelectrochemistry did not appear to have gained the expected attention by the battery research community, despite the fact that these techniques were shown to provide in situ information with spatiotemporal resolution in this field years ago [10–12]. At least two important aspects of nanoelectrochemistry are identified to contribute to it: why and how. On the one hand, the message of why nanoelectrochemistry is necessary in battery research may not have been convincingly transmitted. On the other hand, how nanoelectrochemical measurements are conducted and the differences among the various techniques may not have been sufficiently clear for nonspecialized scientists.

The overarching aim of this review article is to increase the scientific awareness of why nanoelectrochemistry is important for battery research. In the first part, the unique and relevant information that nanoelectrochemistry provides in battery research is highlighted. In the second part, the various nanoelectrochemical techniques used in battery research so far are revised.

Why is nanoelectrochemistry necessary in battery research?

Electrochemical processes occurring in a battery electrode

Although engineering of the battery cell is very important to improve the overall performance, the properties of the battery active materials, in which electrochemical reactions and energy storage take place, determine key parameters of the battery, for example, cell voltage, energy density, power density, safety, and cycle life. Therefore, more efforts are being devoted to study the intrinsic properties of active materials. However, a battery electrode is an ensemble of thousands of active material particles forming a porous film of tens of micrometers thick (Figure 1). Because energy storage mainly occurs in the bulk of the particles in battery materials (in contrast to capacitive or pseudocapacitive materials in which reactions only occur at the near surface), both electrons and ions must reach the electroactive center located in the bulk of an individual active material (Figure 1) [15]. Because many processes occur simultaneously in a battery electrode, approximations in which processes are neglected are necessary to simplify the evaluation and extract the intrinsic properties. Unfortunately, valid assumptions in other type of substrates/research fields are no longer valid for battery electrodes. Valid assumptions may even vary within the battery field depending on the nature of the active

material. At this point, one can already sense that nanoelectrochemistry is of special interest for battery research. Two exemplary cases are selected and discussed in the following section to illustrate the potential and unique contribution of nanoelectrochemistry in battery research.

Intrinsic kinetics of active materials

Mass (ion) transport in the electrolyte often does not prevent the estimation of kinetic parameters by conventional electroanalytical techniques. However, this is not always the case as for the oxygen reduction reaction [16]. Nanoelectrochemistry has been successfully used in those cases in which mass transport plays a critical role [17–19]. For conventional battery electrodes, mass transport is known to limit battery performance when fast charging or low temperatures are required [20–22]. However, it is usually neglected when evaluating the properties of active materials. Electron transport to the electroactive center is usually not an issue in standard electrochemical measurements. However, electrons must cross many solid–solid interfaces to reach the active center in the case of battery electrodes [23]. Again, this parameter is usually disregarded in battery research.

Nanoelectrochemistry addresses simultaneously both issues for the determination of intrinsic kinetics of active materials. The evaluation of a single entity of battery material ensures enough mass transport from the electrolyte and enhances electron transport by reducing significantly the number of solid–solid interfaces. Therefore, nanoelectrochemistry is a reliable and necessary analytical tool for the estimation of intrinsic properties, which are of key importance, for example, when new materials are proposed or storage mechanisms are elucidated.

Figure 1

Involved steps during (de)lithiation. (a) Schematic of a lithium-ion battery being charged. Adapted with permission from Harris et al. [13]. (b) Schematic illustration of a composite electrode in lithium-ion batteries. Adapted with permission from Orkasa et al. [14]. (c) Schematic illustration of possible rate-limiting steps upon lithiation of an intercalation material. Adapted with permission from Löffler et al. [15].

Relationships between the active material structure and electrochemical activity

The electrochemical activity of active battery materials has been proposed to be influenced by the size [24–26] and morphology [26–28]. Tedious experiments were necessary, in which a group of particles with a range of sizes and morphologies are insulated and then evaluated. Even in this case, a range of sizes and morphologies are evaluated together with obtaining the average response of this narrower distribution. Obviously, the evaluation of a single entity is highly desired because it can unravel unexpected behaviors and correlations hindered under the average response of the heterogenous ensemble. The uniqueness of nanoelectrochemistry to elucidate structure–activity correlations has been widely demonstrated in other fields such as electrocatalysis [29–31].

How is nanoelectrochemistry applied in battery research?

Particle-on-a-stick measurements

Fixation of a single particle in a nanoelectrode allows electrochemical evaluation of the individual particle (Figure 2a). The main advantages of this strategy are the following. (1) It does not require complicated instrumentation. (2) The generated electrochemical data are easily evaluated. (3) The particle can be evaluated using basically any type of electroanalytical method (chronoamperometry, cyclic voltammetry, and so on). (4) The particle is easily located for postanalysis, for example,

SEM [32] and transmission electron microscopy [35,36]. Examples of particle-on-a-stick measurements can be found in other fields, for example, electrocatalysis [35–37], but also for battery materials, for example, $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ [32], in which the influence of mass transport was discussed.

There are two major limitations. (1) Fixation of a presynthesized particle, for example, commercial material, is often not possible. (2) The sample preparation is time demanding because each particle needs to be fixed on one small electrode. Therefore, development of a fast and easily implementable universal approach to fix the particle on the electrode will certainly enhance interest in particle-on-a-stick measurements. The use of electrostatic forces appears to be a promising solution [38,39].

Nanoimpact measurements

Instead of fixing a single particle on a small electrode, the electrode is immersed in a suspension of particles. When the suspension is sufficiently diluted, the electrochemistry of a single entity can be evaluated during the short time of the collision with the electrode (Figure 2b) leading to the so-called nanoimpact measurements [40]. The main advantages of nanoimpact measurements are (1) simplicity of the experiment and (2) time-saving property because populations of a large distribution of characteristics are investigated in one single experiment. Nanoimpact measurements are been

Figure 2

Techniques of nanoelectrochemistry. (a) Illustration and SEM images of a particle stuck on a nanoelectrode. Adapted with permission from Clausmeyer et al. [32]. Royal Society of Chemistry. (b) Representation of a single particle collision on an ultramicroelectrode and the corresponding electrochemical response. Adapted with permission from Xiao and Bard [33]. Copyright 2016 American Chemical Society. (c) Schematic of the scanning electrochemical cell microscopy (SECCM) setup, with a transmission electron microscopy (TEM) image of a double-barreled quartz nanopipette (radius, $r = 50$ nm) inset. Adapted with permission from Unwin et al. [34]. Copyright 2016 American Chemical Society. SEM, scanning electron microscopy.

already used to investigate battery materials for aqueous media [41–45] and nonaqueous electrolytes (Li-ion battery electrolyte) [15].

The main limitations are as follows: (1) some electro-analytical methods are restricted owing to the short duration of the particle–electrode interaction and (2) the generated data are not simple to be analyzed by nonspecialists. The development of easy-to-use data analysis software for data analysis of nanoimpact measurements will certainly encourage the use of this powerful tool in a variety of fields including battery research.

Scanning electrochemical probe microscopy

A third option to study the electrochemical activity of single entities of battery materials is to use scanning electrochemical probe microscopy. The scanning electrochemical microscopy has been widely used to investigate battery electrodes, providing unique in situ and spatiotemporal resolved information [46]. However, the lateral resolution is still not sufficiently high to investigate single nanoparticles. The scanning electrochemical cell microscopy (SECCM) has emerged as a very suitable technique for the study of single entities [47]. The high lateral resolution of SECCM has been widely shown in other electrochemical processes [48–50]. There are several relevant examples of the successful application of SECCM for battery research [51–54]. Recently, SECCM was also installed inside an Ar-filled glove box to investigate the Li-ion battery electrode in nonaqueous electrolytes [55]. The main advantages are as follows: (1) the electrochemical activity of single particles can be evaluated by any conventional electroanalytical method, (2) the generated data are easy to be analyzed, and (3) the technique is fast and time-saving (many single particles can be evaluated in one single experiment).

The main limitation of SECCM for battery research is probably the perception of highly specialized instrumentation. Considering the potential of this technique, initial collaborations between battery and analytical chemistry communities are highly encouraged to break down this perception.

Conclusions and outlook

Conventional evaluation of macroelectrodes in battery research often prevents unambiguous determination of intrinsic properties of active materials. However, improvements in battery performances require reliable acquisition of intrinsic properties of active materials for a variety of purposes ranging from modelling, electrode design, material selection, battery management, and so on. For example, when a high value is reliably determined for the diffusion coefficient in the active material, mass transport through the battery electrode will be

the diffusion-limiting step so that special attention must be paid to porosity/tortuosity of this porous electrode. Otherwise, denser and more compact electrodes could be pursued because diffusion inside the particle will anyways be the limiting aspect. Consequently, nanoelectrochemistry in battery research is necessary to deconvolute the various contributions to the average response obtained using conventional macroscopic ensembles of active materials. This step is of essential importance for understanding bottlenecks and storage mechanisms of the battery electrode, which in turn will lead us to better batteries.

There are at least three mature techniques available to conduct nanoelectrochemical measurements in battery research, that is, particle-on-a-stick measurements, nanoimpact measurements, and scanning electrochemical probe microscopy, each of them possessing intrinsic pros and cons. The various examples of unique information provided by these techniques will eventually bring the attention of the battery community. Still, there are two critical aspects for this to finally occur: (1) to find the right example that will mark a turning point and (2) to simplify the methods to facilitate its use by nonspecialists.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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